

USE OF OPTICAL FIBRE SENSORS TO DETECT AND MONITOR DAMAGE IN BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIRS OF CRACKED METALLIC COMPONENTS

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SUMMARY: The application of bonded composite patches to repair or reinforce defective metallic structures is becoming recognised as a very effective versatile procedure for many types of problems. Immediate applications of bonded patch applications are in the fields of repair of cracking, localised reinforcement after removal of corrosion damage and for reduction of fatigue strain. The goal for very demanding repair applications is to incorporate sensors, actuators and electronics in repair systems - smart repair systems - to monitor and report on the health of the repair and the repaired structure, as well as to actuate in order to prevent damage or failure of the repaired structure. The current research is mainly focusing on the assessment of new sensors which may be incorporated in bonded repair systems in order to achieve in-situ real-time measurement of patch integrity and effectiveness. This application would allow the operator to move away from current costly time-based maintenance procedures toward real-time health condition monitoring of the bonded repair and the repaired structure. These systems would allow timely decisions on preventative and schedule maintenance before failure of the repair or repaired structure.

A study was conducted in evaluating the use of embedded and surface mounted optical fibre sensors in detecting and monitoring crack growth of cracked metallic structures repaired with bonded patches. Techniques for embedding optical fibres in boron fibre/epoxy resin patches were developed in this work. The experimental work on a crack patched specimen has shown that optical fibre sensors embedded in composite patches have the potential to detect and monitor crack growth in the metallic sub-structure.

KEYWORDS: smart structures, smart materials, optical fibre sensors, smart patches, intelligent materials and structures

INTRODUCTION

There is a current trend of operating aircraft past their original design life, which has resulted in an increase in the number of structurally significant defects. This problem is extremely relevant to the RAAF where a large number of aircraft, such as the F-111, P3C, Macchi, etc., will have exceeded their original design life before a replacement is put into service. Therefore, the application of bonded composite patches to fix defective structures will become an ever increasing occurrence. However, the application of bonded repairs to primary structures is restricted by certification concerns. For example, the bonded repair on the F-111c wing skin has been substantiated by a substantial analysis and testing program to

ascertain 1) residual strengths, 2) damage tolerance and 3) durability. This approach will be needed for most critical repairs, meaning that feasible repairs may not be undertaken in the future due to the high development costs required to substantiate these types of repairs.

Damage tolerance and durability concerns (i.e., environmental durability and damage resistance of the bond) can be partially overcome by monitoring the condition of the patch during service. In other words, embedding sensors in the patch would allow in-situ NDI to be undertaken on the patch in order to monitor its condition, either on-line or off-line. This approach would considerably ease the operator's concerns during service. Interrogation of the patch, in-situ, should be able to assess 1) crack growth rates and 2) quality of the bond.

Fibre optic technology offers a means by which these essential functions can be performed through the use of embedded fibre optic sensors. Fibre optic sensors (FOSs) offer a new approach to this problem and should allow continuous, in-situ condition monitoring. FOSs offer the advantage of being able to be embedded in a patch without degrading its mechanical properties. Other advantages of FOSs include:

- extreme sensitivity (sensitivity is increased if the sensors are embedded)
- robustness
- monitor temperature for cure purposes
- monitor residual strains in patch (during curing and during service)
- on-line or off-line sensing in-situ

To implement FOSs in composite patches there are a number of factors which need to be addressed. These include the (1) practicality of fabrication, (2) performance (i.e. sensitivity, maximum strain, durability of the fibre, etc.), (3) optimisation (i.e. location, sensing length, etc.) and (4) effects on the mechanical properties of the composite.

The aim of this project is to evaluate the practicality of fabrication and performance of FOSs, embedded in two composite patches and surface bonded to one composite patch, for monitoring the growth of a crack in a metallic structure. As part of the investigations, sensors were embedded or surface bonded at various locations and with various sensing lengths in order to determine the optimum location of application and sensing length. This paper will only report on the embedded sensor results.

TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

Foptic™ Vibration Sensor

Multimode fibre optic sensors generally suffer from optical signal fading and drift. The optical fibre industry has overcome the inherent weaknesses of multimode fibres by the use of singlemode fibre systems, but these are more difficult to handle, and utilise quite expensive components. This significant disadvantage offsets the multimode fibre's advantages of low cost and ease of application.

In recent years, Future Fibre Technologies (FFT) has developed the Foptic™ Vibration Sensor. Based on a unique fibre optic modalmetric sensor configuration, it overcomes the inherent weaknesses of multimode fibre optic sensors, is easy to fabricate and costs relatively little to assemble. The Foptic™ Vibration Sensor provides the first fibre optic sensor in the world which offers an inexpensive method for producing truly localised and mechanically

stable fibre optic multimode sensors, with the flexibility to use virtually any desired optical fibre and components. Fig. 1 illustrates the general configuration of the Foptic™ Vibration Sensor.

Fig. 1: Foptic™ Vibration Sensor configuration.

The Foptic™ Vibration Sensor is best suited for dynamic measurements. The Foptic™ Vibration Sensor response is a direct function of the dynamic disturbance on the sensitised portion of the fibre. The disturbance may be in the form of physical movement (ie., compression (radially or axially), elongation, twisting or vibration) or microphonic effects (ie., travelling stress waves or acoustic emissions). In the experimental arrangement used in this project, the dynamic elongation and longitudinal compression of the sensitised portion of the fibre results in load-dependent strains in the optical fibre which create intensity modulations. These intensity modulations (the sensor's response) can be measured and calibrated to the known loads or to co-located reference electrical strain gauges.

SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

Preliminary Study

Preliminary work studied the feasibility of embedding fibre optic sensors in boron/epoxy (B/E) laminates and in FM73 film adhesive. Standard telecommunications optical fibre with 125/250 μm cladding/buffer diameter was used. The cladding and buffer material was glass and acrylate, respectively. A square B/E specimen, consisting of five unidirectional plies, was prepared and cured under standard conditions. The optical fibres were embedded co-linearly with the boron fibres between the first and second plies, as well as the fourth and fifth plies, during the lay-up procedure. The fibres were embedded in pairs and the distance between the fibres was varied between 0.1 and 2 mm. In order to provide strain relief to these optical fibres, where they exited the material, approximately 2 to 3 mm of the buffered section of the fibres was embedded in the composite. Two sensors with buffer included, fibres 1 and 2, were embedded between the fourth and fifth plies. Owing to the arrangement used, the transmissive-mode sensors had an entry point into the composite as well as an exit point on the opposite side of the specimen. In addition, a reflective-mode sensor (fibre mirrored on end face) was embedded between the third and fourth plies. Fig. 2 illustrates the top and cross-sectional views of the embedding arrangement, respectively.

Following cure, visible laser light was launched into each input fibre of the transmissive-mode sensors and the output fibres were observed in order to determine if the sensor had survived the curing procedure. All ten transmissive-mode sensors had survived the cure. The reflective-mode sensor was connected to the Foptic™ Vibration Monitor unit and was tested. Two unbuffered optical fibres were also placed between two layers of the FM-73 adhesive and this arrangement was co-cured between two pieces of thin aluminium. These fibres were not tested for through-put, due to the success rate of the work with the B/E. The B/E and FM-

73 specimens were then cut-up into several pieces, with the saw-lines perpendicular to the optical fibre direction. Each specimen was then polished for viewing under an optical microscope. Fig. 3 shows typical macrographs of the cross-sectional views.

Fig. 2: (a) Top and (b) cross-sectional view of boron/epoxy laminate with embedded optical fibres.

Fig. 3: (a) Buffered fibres, fibres 1/2, embedded in the B/E laminate. (b) Unbuffered fibres, fibres 3/4, at 0.7 mm spacing in the B/E laminate.

From these macrographs the following points were observed:

1. No significant difficulties were encountered during the installation or fabrication stages. All the fibres, emerging from the B/E, remained intact and rugged, and showed no signs of brittleness.
2. The relatively-large diameter buffered fibre significantly displaced the surrounding material fibres, see Fig. 3a. It was concluded that only unbuffered fibre should be used.
3. The unbuffered fibres, having approximately the same diameter as the boron fibres, did not significantly effect the arrangement of the surrounding material fibres when the optical fibres were located around 1 mm or greater apart (see optical fibres 3 and 4 in Fig. 3b). However, if the unbuffered optical fibres were placed much less than 1 mm apart they did have some effect on the surrounding material fibres. It was concluded that the optical fibres should not be embedded closer than 1 mm from each other, in B/E.
4. During the cure process, the scrim of the ply above an optical fibre tended to push the fibre downwards into the ply below and the scrim of the ply below a fibre tended to restrict its downward movement to within the corresponding ply, as seen in Fig. 3b.
5. The two fibres embedded in the FM-73 moved downwards into the bottom layer by the same distance.

Crack Patched Specimens

Standard telecommunications optical fibre with 125/250 μm cladding/buffer diameter was used. The cladding and buffer material was glass and acrylate, respectively. The sensors were individually tested and monitored using the Foptictm Vibration Monitor unit before and during the installation process to ensure that all the sensors were operative prior to the cure process.

Fig. 4: (a) Schematic of the specimen used for this experimental program. (b) Photograph of the boron/epoxy repaired specimen with embedded optical fibre sensors.

The two test specimens were specified and manufactured and consisted of two cracked aluminium panels, with a B/E patch over the crack, tested back-to-back using a honeycomb sandwich panel, as shown schematically in Fig. 3a. The semi-circular B/E patches were constructed in a 7 ply, unidirectional (i.e., $[0]_7$) laminate arrangement and were adhered to the aluminium panel with two layers of FM-73 adhesive. The patches were constructed in a tapered arrangement, with a radius of curvature of 75 mm for the largest ply and 60 mm for the smallest ply.

The optical fibres were embedded co-linearly with the boron fibres. In order to provide strain relief to these optical fibres, where they exited the material, approximately 2 to 3 mm of the buffered section of the fibres was embedded in the composite. Precautionary measures were taken to prevent the epoxy from running along the optical fibres (by capillary action) during the cure process, because, once cured, the epoxy is brittle and could also make the optical fibres brittle. This was achieved by placing teflon tape over sections of the fibres close to the patch and creating dams with a high temperature vacuum sealant. Previous work taught us that preventing the epoxy from running along the fibre helps to maintain the fibres flexibility and strength. Once the patches were cured, they were prepared for attachment to the cracked metallic test specimen. One patch was co-cured to the cracked metallic test specimen (side B) and the second patch was simultaneously secondary bonded to the same cracked metallic test specimen (side A). Following the final cure process, the sensors were connected to the Foptictm Vibration Monitor unit and tested in order to determine if the sensors had survived the curing procedure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Jacketed, connectorised fibre optic leads were fusion spliced to all the FOSs which had survived the installation and attachment procedures, in order to couple the sensors to the Foptictm Vibration Monitor units. The linearity of the Foptictm Vibration Sensor response has been shown to be good over a 1000+ $\mu\epsilon$ range in other work. However, the sensor must be calibrated to obtain quantitative results. The results obtained with the FOSs in this work may be approximated with respect to the known loads applied with the hydraulic uniaxial testing machine or, preferably, the localised strain measured by the reference electrical strain gauges (ESGs). However, it is difficult to make a generalised calibration on the Foptictm Vibration Sensor without the sensors being exactly co-located (such that they both experience the exact same strain/load conditions). This is difficult to achieve, particularly with regard to the embedded FOSs, and generally impractical in field conditions. However, the synchronised, relative peak-to-peak values of the two sensor responses (FOSs and ESGs) may be compared over time, during fatigue cycling, to determine whether the in-situ strain conditions monitored by the FOS are changing as the crack in the test specimen grows. This may be useful in determining whether there is a general trend in the FOS response as the crack tip in the specimen approaches and passes the location of the FOS, since the localised strains vary significantly as this occurs. This technique is used to assess the response of the FOS to crack growth.

Fig. 5: (a) Position of FOSA, FOSB and FOSC on specimen. (b) Side A and (c) Side B with foil strain gauges ESGA, B and C indicated.

In all the testing, the FOS signals were captured and displayed on an AMLAB[®] I digital signal processing workstation. Sometimes the signals were Fast Fourier Transform analysed and recorded in real-time in order to determine the frequency characteristics of the sensor signals. This was carried-out mainly to confirm the frequency of the applied load, when appropriate. Three ESGs were attached to the test specimen, at various locations, in order to compare the responses of the sensors. Diagrams of the locations of FOSs and strain gauges on side A (side with secondary bonded patch) and side B (side with co-cured patch) are illustrated in Fig. 5. The responses of ESGs were simultaneously captured, displayed and recorded for comparison with the FOSs.

The test specimens were subjected to tension-dominated fatigue loading, at a frequency of 3 to 4 Hz, using a 250 kN capacity Instron hydraulic uniaxial testing machine. Initially, a static pre-load of 77 kN was applied and then it was subjected to tensile-dominated cyclic load of ± 63 kN for a total of 190,000 cycles. The initial crack length was 10 mm. At every 5,000 cycles, the testing was paused and a crack measurement was made manually using an eddy current probe. In addition, static strain surveys were performed with the ESGs at various stages of the testing, and manually recorded.

The signals from the three FOSs and the three ESGs, shown in Fig. 5, were captured and displayed in real-time using the AMLAB[®] unit. Since the data acquisition unit has only four analog input channels, it was decided to monitor the three FOSs with the first three channels and the three ESG signals were captured, one at a time (in turn), using the fourth available channel. Recordings of the sensors signals were made every 1,000 cycles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Embedding FOS in Boron/Epoxy Patches

Following the curing process, many of the optical fibre leads of both patches showed significant signs of brittleness and several fibres were visibly damaged. Furthermore, the fibre buffer appeared to be considerably deformed and was even absent in some regions of the fibre. Neither of these problems had been encountered in previous work. At this stage, we realised that a previously unencountered factor was acting to significantly degrade the acrylate buffer and weaken the optical fibres.

Previous work with graphite/epoxy and boron/epoxy laminates yielded 100% embedded sensor survivability. However it now appears that the volatile chemicals produced or released from the FM-73 adhesive during cure (in particular, methyl ethyl ketone - MEK) may have reacted with the acrylate coating of the optical fibres and significantly weakened the sensors. This conclusion was strengthened by the fact that less than 50% of sensors survived on the side of the patch closest to the vacuum port, whereas over 70% survived on the opposite side. This was considered relevant because any volatiles produced during cure would tend to migrate towards the vacuum port as the vacuum was being applied and so would run along the fibre in the process. In addition, this conclusion was also supported by the fact that the majority of fibres failed near the edge of the secondary bonded patch, and mostly on the side closest to the vacuum port. Therefore, any future work involving FM-73, will necessitate the use extra precautions to protect the integrity of the optical fibres with the acrylate coating or to use an optical fibre with a more rugged buffer material, such as polyimide. However,

polyimide is much more difficult to work with than acrylate and will significantly increase the time required to fabricate the sensors and install them in composites.

Dynamic Fatigue Test Results

As expected, the strains measured with ESGA remained relatively constant throughout the test. However, the strains measured by ESGB approximately doubled during testing from 40,000 cycles to 150,000 cycles, as illustrated in Fig. 6, and the residual strain detected at the end of testing was quite significant (178 $\mu\epsilon$). The background noise of the optical fibre system was negligible, unless the AMLAB[®] gain was increased significantly in order to determine the minimum sensitivity of the FOSs. The signal-to-noise ratios of FOSA and FOSB were typically in the same range as the surface bonded ESGs. The signal-to-noise ratio for FOSC, however, was lower but reasonable.

The responses from the FOSs represent the localised strain and bending effects acting on the fibre. Any changes in the sensor's signal is a direct indication that a condition has changed, no matter how unusual or unexpected those signals may be. As previously discussed, the Foptic[™] Vibration Sensor must be calibrated to obtain quantitative results. The results obtained with the FOSs in this work may be approximated with respect to the localised strains measured by the reference ESGs. However, it is difficult to make a generalised calibration on the Foptic[™] Vibration Sensor without the sensors being exactly co-located (such that they both experience the exact same strain/load conditions). This is difficult to achieve, particularly with regard to the embedded FOSs. Nonetheless, the synchronised, relative peak-to-peak values of the two sensor responses (FOSs and ESGs) may be compared over time, during fatigue cycling, to determine whether the in-situ strain conditions monitored by the FOS are changing as the crack in the test specimen grows. This may be useful in determining whether there is a general trend in the FOS response as the crack tip in the specimen approaches and passes the location of the FOS, since the localised strains vary significantly as this occurs.

The peak-to-peak values of the signals were calculated at each 1,000 cycle interval. These values were then plotted as a function of the number of fatigue cycles for each sensor. Fig. 6 - 9 illustrate the peak-to-peak responses of the FOSs and ESGs as a function of the number of fatigue cycles. The response of ESGA remained relatively constant. On the other hand, the response of ESGB increased linearly throughout the test and nearly doubled in amplitude by the end of the testing. The response from ESGC showed a slight downward trend until N=164,000 and CLA=39 mm, where it began a slight trend upwards, at approximately the same slope as ESGB.

As can be seen in Fig. 7, the peak-to-peak responses of all three FOSs showed significant downwards trends at the start of the testing, until approximately N=57,000 cycles and CLA=16 mm, and then underwent several changes for the remainder of the testing. In Fig. 8, the peak-to-peak response of FOSB is illustrated. The sensor's response decreased until approximately N=67,000 cycles and CLA=17.5 mm. The sensor's response then increased linearly until a sudden, large decrease at approximately N=121,000 cycles and CLA=30 mm. The decrease in response continued in a linear manner until N=133,000 cycles and CLA=32 mm, which is exactly where the sensor was located, when it suddenly increased in the exact same manner as it had decreased. As can be seen in the figure, the decrease and then increase in the sensor's response, centred about N=133,000 cycles, was symmetric about the vertical direction. At N=148,000 cycles and CLA=34 mm the signal from FOSB decreased by one

order of magnitude, suggesting that the sudden increase in strains may have damaged the fibre or that the fibre may have disbonded from the B/E matrix. The latter explanation is more probable since the sensor was still detecting a sinusoidal signal, whereas a fractured fibre would not respond at all. In any case, it may be concluded that FOSB's response showed a definite trend as the crack approached and passed the location of the sensor.

In Fig. 9, the peak-to-peak response of FOSA is illustrated. The sensor's response decreased until approximately $N=58,000$ cycles and a crack length on side B (CLB) of 16.5 mm, close to where the sensor was located. The sensor's response then increased linearly in the same manner as it had decreased until approximately $N=67,000$ cycles and $CLB=19$ mm, where it began to modulate. At approximately $N=98,000$ cycles and $CLB=25$ mm, the sensor's response settled and decreased until approximately $N=140,000$ cycles and $CLB=34.5$ mm, where it began to increase and then modulate further. As can be seen in the figure, the decrease and then increase in the sensor's response, centred about $N=58,000$ cycles, was symmetric about the vertical direction, as was the case for FOSB when the crack approached and passed its location. This suggests that FOSA's response showed a trend as the crack approached and passed the location of the sensor, although it was not as clear as the case with FOSB.

Fig. 6: Electrical strain gauge response versus fatigue cycles.

Fig. 7: FoptiC™ Vibration Sensor response versus fatigue cycles

Fig. 8: Response of FOSB and ESGC to crack growth.

Fig. 9: Response of FOSA and ESGB to crack growth.

During fatigue loading, it was noted that the B/E patch was undergoing considerable bending in the region near the base of the crack (the edge of the specimen with the start of the crack),

particularly once the crack length grew beyond 20 mm. Since FOSC was embedded within this region it too was subjected to these bending effects. Therefore, FOSC was actually responding to both the tensile loading as well as the bending effects. In fact all sensors experience significant local secondary bending as the crack passes under them. It is suspected that this may help to explain the quality of the response of the sensor.

CONCLUSION

A number of Foptic™ Vibration Sensors were embedded in two boron/epoxy patches during the lay-up stage. The two patches were then cured and prepared for attachment to a cracked metallic test specimen. One patch was co-cured to the cracked metallic test specimen and the second patch was simultaneously secondary bonded to the same cracked metallic test specimen. Considerable difficulties were encountered with fibres failing during the various cure stages of the B/E patches. Although previous work with graphite/epoxy and boron/epoxy patches yielded 100% embedded sensor survivability, in this case a low percentage of fibres survived the cure stages. It is believed that the volatile chemicals produced or released from the FM-73 adhesive during cure reacted with the acrylate coating of the optical fibres and significantly weakened the sensors. It is recommended that work involving FM-73 will require enhanced protection of the fibres with the acrylate coating or to use an optical fibre with a more rugged buffer material, such as polyimide.

The test specimen with the three embedded fibre optic sensors was fatigued. Three electrical strain gauges were also attached to the specimen as reference strain gauges. The results of the fatigue testing clearly demonstrate that the responses of the embedded fibre optic sensors underwent significant changes as the length of the crack increased. Furthermore, the analysis of the sensors' responses indicate that the fibre optic sensors exhibited distinct trends as the crack approached and passed the location of the embedded sensors. The 4 mm long sensors required higher gains than the longer sensors and often displayed a lower signal-to-noise ratio. The responses from the 16 mm long sensors were not as consistent as the 8 mm long sensors, perhaps because they integrated many signals or effects over their relatively long lengths. The 8 mm long sensors appeared to perform relatively well and had good signal-to-noise ratios.

During the testing, it was observed that the B/E patches were undergoing considerable bending in the region near the base of the cracks. It is suspected that the bending effects on the B/E patches may have contributed to the response characteristics of the sensors and that this may have had a significantly higher effect on the response of the shorter sensors. Overall the test series demonstrated that the Foptic™ Vibration Sensor technology has good potential for monitoring the crack growth of a crack in a metallic structure, although embedding procedures for the fibre optic sensors must be improved.

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